

Non-standard layer of English lexicon

Sultonqulova Gulzodakhan Avazjon qizi

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

Magistratura 2-kurs filologiya (ingliz tili) fakulteti talabasi

Abstract: This article provides valuable insight into the hierarchical structure of the English language and explains non-literary vocabulary as a modern medium of communication. In addition, this article promotes non-standard vocabulary types, identifies them by characteristics, and provides examples of each.

Key words: English, vocabulary, atypical, non-literary, literature, foreign language, terminology, terminology.

After the proclamation of Uzbekistan's independence, the need for English as a means of communication increased rapidly. Currently, various educational institutions and governments are striving to promote mastery of English as a second language at all levels of the country. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the stylistic concept of the language, which is wide and in demand all over the world. National focus on the study and analysis of the English language.

It is known that the English language consists of three main stylistic hierarchies: the neutral class, the literary class, and the conversational class. Some layers only deal with the literary language, but one of them is a slang layer containing a set of words that includes slang, jargon, dialects, and other types of non-literary vocabulary. Since this is the main topic of this article, non-literary vocabulary is also called non-standard vocabulary. It is believed that non-standard vocabulary is mainly used for communication in oral discourse, because it is more fluid than in formal written discourse. However, it is very difficult to distinguish between these layers of the spoken language. Moreover, this differentiation has become one of the biggest problems in the study of the English style.

It is important to use jargon when referring to certain slang. Terminology is considered one of the largest non-standard vocabularies used mainly by people of certain social groups. According to the dictionary, jargon is a widely used term that defines words that appear in any language, and its function is to protect the privacy of small social groups. In general, terminology differs in that it takes on a completely new meaning compared to its original meaning. It is difficult for people from different subcultures, societies and countries to understand jargon, because it is the application of existing words in completely new forms and meanings to a small number of people.

For example, when it comes to jargon, simple words that have meaning due to codes or special additions may contain additional words that make those words unique and may only be recognized by some people who are already familiar with these codes. As a popular terminology, we can offer you a selection of generally accepted terminology "money". Some social groups call money "fat". In addition, the popular word "military" is also used as jargon because the literary equivalent of the word is called "military." As you can see from this example, not all of the jargon in the table is difficult to understand. On the other hand, it is sometimes difficult to distinguish between the technical terms "military" and "military", and sometimes there is confusion as to whether these words are technical terms at all.

The next type of non-standard English vocabulary is slang. Slang is a term used in languages other than standard English vocabulary. As the 21st century has taken a revolutionary course with the development of information technology and the Internet, terminology has become widespread in the web space and in the real world. For example, some of the most popular social networks today are Twitter and Instagram, where almost all people between the ages of 20 and 20 communicate with each other verbally and in writing using jargon. In the English language that exists and is widely used today, there are many slang words that have been replaced by literary words. Examples of this phenomenon are the following words: tbh, the term "pronoun", d-formed, canceled, boomer, generation Z, and others. Each of them has a specific meaning, and these words were never used before the Internet and social media were created in their current meaning. As you can see, modern jargon is based on various abbreviations. This indicates that young people want to share information in their heads as quickly as possible without spending too much time writing. TBH is also an acronym for honest. For someone who uses little social media and is unfamiliar with the jargon, it can be difficult to "survive" with simple and widespread literary English words in today's social media space. People who don't know the jargon can get lost in cyberspace. In addition, the word used in the singular sense of "deciding not to have more meetings or parties" has eliminated a completely different meaning for young people. The new definition of "cancellation" is synonymous with "unsubscribe culture", characterized by the fact that someone's ideas and opinions are no longer supported due to someone else's mistakes and indicate a misunderstanding. Globalization and its expanding boundaries allow us to distinguish between jargon and jargon. In addition, the jargon of people belonging to other social groups is somewhat "rude" compared to those who use slang. Finally, there is the word vulgarity. Most of the profanity and words that express people's anger are considered vulgar and therefore are called misleading. Among them can be called "Blood", "Hell", "Hell", etc. Many of these words are indeed found in modern literature of the XX-XXI centuries, suggesting that vulgarity has become a way of expressing strong feelings and emotions.

In conclusion, English cannot be fully understood and understood with literary language alone, and non-standard languages have proven to be more prevalent than literature among the masses. Therefore, it is very important to take into account the widespread use of non-literary words such as slang, slang and vulgar words in the methodology and process of teaching

English. These words convey the same meaning as other literary words, and in some cases more than in the literary language. In conclusion, the problem of non-standard languages should always be regarded as one of the important problems of linguistics and style.

References

1. Migdadi, H. F., Yunus, K., & Al.Garni, A.-F. (2020). A Global View towards Understanding of Standard and Non-Standard Varieties of English. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 103–115.
2. Richard Sproat, Alan W. Black, Stanley Chen, Shankar Kumar, Mari Ostendorf, Christopher Richards, Normalization of non-standard words, *Computer Speech & Language*, Volume 15, Issue 3, 2001, Pages 287-333, ISSN 0885-2308,
3. <http://linguistics-elenapoparcea.blogspot.com/2012/01/three-main-layers-of-english-language.html>
4. Prato, Francesca. (2016). 'All Englishes are equal': an analysis on Standard and non-Standard English.
5. Migdadi, Hamzah & Yunus, Kamariah & Al.Garni, Abdul-Fattah. (2020). A Global View towards Understanding of Standard and Non-Standard Varieties of English. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 10. 103-115. 10.6007/IJARBS/v10-i2/6894.